

Psychosocial Vulnerability and Depression in Adolescents: The Mediating Role of Perceived Parental Digital Support and the Moderating Role of Online Socio-Emotional Regulation

Code R studio Versión 2025.09.2+418 (2025.09.2+418)

Mediation Anlysis

Model 4 Hayes (Hayes, 2018):

```
library(processR)
```

```
# Miedo al rechazo * Supervisión Familiar * Depresión
```

```
process(  
  data = Data_RStudio,  
  y = "ZDepr",  
  x = "ZMied",  
  m = "ZSupF",  
  cov = "Edad",  
  model = 4,  
)
```

```
# Necesidad de Pertenencia * Supervisión Familiar * Depresión
```

```
process(  
  data = Data_RStudio,  
  y = "ZDepr",  
  x = "ZNec",  
  m = "ZSupF",  
  cov = "Edad",  
  model = 4,  
)
```

```
# Comparación Social * Supervisión Familiar * Depresión
```

```
process(  
  data = Data_RStudio,  
  y = "ZDepr",  
  x = "ZComSoc",  
  m = "ZSupF",
```

```
cov = "Edad",  
model = 4,  
)
```

Moderate Mediation

Model 15 (Hayes, 2018):

```
library(processR)  
# Necesidad * Depresión * e-Auton  
process(  
  data = Data_RStudio,  
  y = "ZDepr",  
  x = "ZNec",  
  m = "ZSupF",  
  w = "ZeAut",  
  cov = "Edad",  
  model = 15,  
)
```

Comparación Social* Depresión * e-Auton

```
process(  
  data = Data_RStudio,  
  y = "ZDepr",  
  x = "ZComSoc",  
  m = "ZSupF",  
  w = "ZeAut",  
  cov = "Edad",  
  model = 15,  
)
```

Miedo al rechazo* Depresión * e-Auton

```
process(  
  data = Data_RStudio,  
  y = "ZDepr",  
  x = "ZMied",  
  m = "ZSupF",  
  w = "ZeAut",  
  cov = "Edad",  
  model = 15,  
)
```

```
# Necesidad * Depresión * e-Regulación
```

```
process(  
  data = Data_RStudio,  
  y = "ZDepr",  
  x = "ZNec",  
  m = "ZSupF",  
  w = "ZeRe",  
  cov = "Edad",  
  model = 15,  

```

```
)
```

```
# Comparación Social * Depresión * e-Regulación
```

```
process(  
  data = Data_RStudio,  
  y = "ZDepr",  
  x = "ZComSoc",  
  m = "ZSupF",  
  w = "ZeRe",  
  cov = "Edad",  
  model = 15,  

```

```
)
```

```
# Miedo al rechazo* Depresión * e-Regulación
```

```
process(  
  data = Data_RStudio,  
  y = "ZDepr",  
  x = "ZMied",  
  m = "ZSupF",  
  w = "ZeRe",  
  cov = "Edad",  
  model = 15,  

```

```
)
```

```
# Necesidad * Depresión * e-Control de los impulsos
```

```
process(  
  data = Data_RStudio,  
  y = "ZDepr",  
  x = "ZNec",  
  m = "ZSupF",  
  w = "ZeIMP",  

```

```

cov = "Edad",
model = 15,

)

# Comparación Social * Depresión * e-Control de los impulsos
process(
  data = Data_RStudio,
  y = "ZDepr",
  x = "ZComSoc",
  m = "ZSupF",
  w = "ZeIMP ",
  cov = "Edad",
  model = 15,
)

```

```

# Miedo al rechazo* Depresión * e-Control de los impulsos

```

```

process(
  data = Data_RStudio,
  y = "ZDepr",
  x = "ZMied",
  m = "ZSupF",
  w = " ZeIMP",
  cov = "Edad",
  model = 15,
)

```

Graphics

```

library(ggplot2)

```

```

# Valores de PROCESS para el efecto de ZSupF en ZDepr a 3 niveles de ZeRe

```

```

cond_effects <- data.frame(
  ZeRe = c(-1.0108, -0.0340, 1.0257), # valores del moderador (W)
  Effect = c(-0.0105, -0.1117, -0.2214), # efecto de ZSupF sobre ZDepr
  SE = c(0.0410, 0.0287, 0.0372)
)

```

```

# Cálculo de intervalos de confianza

```

```

cond_effects$LLCI <- cond_effects$Effect - 1.96 * cond_effects$SE
cond_effects$ULCI <- cond_effects$Effect + 1.96 * cond_effects$SE

```

```

ggplot(cond_effects, aes(x = ZeRe, y = Effect)) +
  geom_line(color = "blue", size = 1) +
  geom_point(size = 3) +
  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin = LLCI, ymax = ULCI), width = 0.05) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 0, linetype = "dashed", color = "grey40") +
  labs(title = "Conditional Effect of Family Support on Depression",
       subtitle = "Moderated by e-Regulation (ZeRe)",
       x = "e-Regulation (ZeRe)",
       y = "Effect of Family Support (ZSupF) on Depression (ZDepr)") +
  theme_minimal()

```

Datos de efectos indirectos a distintos niveles de ZeRe

```

indirect_data <- data.frame(
  ZeRe = c(-1.0108, -0.0340, 1.0257), # valores del moderador
  Effect = c(-0.0009, -0.0096, -0.0190),
  BootSE = c(0.0037, 0.0045, 0.0083),
  BootLLCI = c(-0.0086, -0.0199, -0.0366),
  BootULCI = c(0.0069, -0.0020, -0.0044)
)
ggplot(indirect_data, aes(x = ZeRe, y = Effect)) +
  geom_line(color = "darkgreen", size = 1) +
  geom_point(size = 3) +
  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin = BootLLCI, ymax = BootULCI), width = 0.05) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 0, linetype = "dashed", color = "grey40") +
  labs(title = "Conditional Indirect Effect of Need to Belong on Depression",
       subtitle = "Via Family Support, moderated by e-Regulation (ZeRe)",
       x = "e-Regulation (ZeRe)",
       y = "Indirect Effect (ZNec → ZSupF → ZDepr)") +
  theme_minimal()

```

Crear gráfico de interacción simple

```

library(interactions)
interact_plot(modelo, pred = ZSupF, modx = ZeRe,
  modx.values = c(-1, 0, 1),
  modx.labels = c("Low (-1 DE)", "Mean", "High (+1 DE)"),
  x.label = "Perceived Family Support",
  y.label = "Depression",
  legend.main = "Emotional e-regulation",
  main.title =,
  interval = TRUE, plot.points = FALSE)

```

